

"RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION"

International Conference on Teacher Education

CHARACTERISTICS OF COGNITIVE ABILITY DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS AND PUPILS

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In the Republic of Kazakhstan, comprehensive development of cognitive ability of the future generation and pupils and students and creation of favorable conditions for it is of great importance. Also, in the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Education", one of the principles of state policy is "to encourage the qualification and talent of an individual". it is necessary to develop" - it is stated. [1].

N.A. Nazarbayev's lecture at the Kazakh National University named after Al-Farabi said: "Kazakhstan needs an intellectual revolution that will create conditions for awakening and realizing the potential of our nation."

Our task now is to change and expand the attitudes of pupils, students and young people towards education, patriotism, and service to the people. Therefore, we need to create a pillar of national intelligence. At the same time, we need erudite people who can compete at the international level. [2].

Problems of improving cognitive abilities (thinking ability) can also be found in the works of scientists. For example, A. Aldamuratov, S. M. Zhakypov, V. K. Shabelnikov, T. Sabyrov, etc. studied ways and prerequisites of formation of cognitive activity during training.

The way to increase the effectiveness of teaching is to increase the importance of the moral relationship between the individual personalities of the teacher and the student - psychological cognitive activity. This activity develops between the teacher and the students, is realized through teaching methods and tools, and determines the actual content of teaching. The issues raised above are based on the principles of cooperation pedagogy.

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According to the opinion of the scientist T. Sabyrov: "the teacher connects his actions in educating students with the guidance of children's cognitive actions through the teaching method" [3].

We understand that the teacher, acting as a regulator and guide, uses teaching methods as a tool to improve children's cognitive activity.

In the scientific work of S.K. Berdybaeva, O.S. Sangylbaev, M.O. Rezvantseva various psychological functions, laws of formation processes and ways of their development in teaching activities, etc. the following issues were raised.

Also, M. Mukanov, N. Aigabylov, Z.Y. Namazbaeva, N.K. Toksanbaeva, etc. a number of scientists have conducted scientific research on improving mental cognitive processes of students, including thinking abilities.

Z.Y. Namazbaeva "Development of personality in mentally retarded schools" [4], gives special importance to the personality formation of children with mental and intellectual disabilities by taking into account their abilities and their moral attitude.

The author believes that such children's correct acceptance of the evaluations and opinions of others, the ability of the child to make demands and look critically at his own actions, has a positive effect on his intellectual development.

And if optimal intellectual development opens the way to good opportunities and knows how to set limits, then the way for the child to become an individual will be opened, - he claims.

Native scientist N.K. Toksanbaeva believes: "The effectiveness of teaching depends on the correct organization of children's higher mental functions - thinking, attention, memory, and children's cognitive activities are particularly important in the teaching process" [5].

In his work, the author collected the research works of Russian and Kazakhstan scientists and compiled methods for checking, developing and correcting the mental processes of students.

Famous Kazakh psychologist M. M. Mukanov said: "Language is a vehicle, thought is a passenger, everyone's head (mind) is a station. Everyone's mind rides the language car and moves from one station to another" [6].

A child's propensity to a certain activity becomes known from a young age. Therefore, in Kazakh, there are sayings: "a child will be born from kindergarten", "a child will be born from the age of five".

Attitude, ability is a person's tendency to engage in a certain activity, attention to it, that is, the first sign of awakening ability. Therefore, the tendency observed in

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childhood-Don't forget that your skills are the prerequisites for your abilities in the future. And all human abilities originate from thinking and mental activity.

The most important wealth of any state in the world is a person and his good life. All the achievements that have been achieved so far are the result of the work of the human race. In the era of globalization, life requires us to be mobile, to make quick decisions and move to specific actions. However, it is a fact that we often encounter inhumane and moral-humane principles in order to stay out of the flow of life. Education is a social process, it cannot be considered in isolation from society. Its main dimension is the development of personal qualities necessary for life [7].

We believe that one of the ways to solve these problems is to strengthen moral education for young people. This is because the main principle of morality is to teach others to see themselves as you do, to encourage people to care for those around them.

Another phenomenon that has gained a special momentum in Kazakhstan is that young students are strongly devoted to religion and join sects. On the one hand, young people have turned to religion in order to be polite, and it seems that they have entered the path of morality. On the other hand, it can be observed that under the guise of religion, separation from relatives, disobedience to parents, and disobedience to state laws and regulations have become a habit.

To sum up, there is one big problem here, it is to follow the ignorant and uneducated people without knowing the religion well, and to follow their shadow. Once upon a time, the famous Russian writer Leo Tolstoy praised Islam: "The culmination of the mind of any rational person comes to Islam." Let's hope that our youth, pupils and students will have a high future, a bright future, and mature into sensible citizens and citizens, as Leo Tolstoy said, brothers.

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